

Blind Channel Estimation for Audio Signals²

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Abstract—This research presents a new approach for blind channel estimation for audio signals. For most speech processing techniques such as speech recognition or speaker identification, the performance can drop significantly when the statistics of the training data such as the channel shape, noise, and distortion differ from the statistics of the testing data. Aside from the standard technique of cepstral mean normalization, few techniques are available for reducing channel mismatch conditions. Experimental results will be presented for both channel estimation and for channel normalization via inverse filtering where the inverse filter is derived from the channel estimate.

Telephone data is also examined.

The second thrust uses the channel estimates to perform inverse filtering in an effort to restore frequency information. Speaker identification experiments are used as a performance measure for the estimation technique.

Section 2 presents the technique of blindly estimating a channel for an audio signal. Section 3 demonstrates how this technique is able to accurately estimate linear channels.

Section 4 and 5 applies this technique to telephone data which has channel effects, noise, and other non-linear distortion. Section 6 summarizes the research and suggests some future research.

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1. INTRODUCTION

While many techniques have been applied towards improving performance by reducing mismatch conditions, such as RASTA filtering, liftering, and delta cepstral features, these techniques provide only limited improvement. The standard normalization technique is still the cepstral normalization process even though it removes some of the speech information.

Two thrusts are examined in this paper. The first thrust is to develop a technique to estimate a linear channel. The experiments will start with clean, wideband data and apply a known linear channel to it. Thus, it is a controlled experiment designed to gauge the accuracy of this technique.

2. BLIND CHANNEL ESTIMATION

If a linear channel is assumed, the equation for audio data is:

$$y = h * x \quad (1)$$

where y is the channel-corrupted audio, h is the linear channel, and x is the input. While telephone bandwidths tend to be between 300-3400 Hertz, the passband region can be quite different. For example, Figure 1a shows a typical carbon-button microphone and Figure 1b shows a typical electret microphone. Obviously, the passband response and attenuation for each microphone is quite different. Thus, for a general solution, one can not assume anything about the channel characteristics.

For the speech signal, x , it is also difficult to make any assumptions. If the data is text-dependent, it may be more feasible to obtain an estimate of x , but, once again, this does not lead to a general solution.

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Figure 1. Carbon-button vs. Electret microphone.

Smoothed Estimate of y

The goal of this research is to develop techniques for blindly estimating h given only y . Obviously, this is a very difficult task and, as discussed in Section 1.1, it is difficult to make any assumptions about either h or x . However, before attempting to estimate either h or x , it is important to take a close look at the observed signal, y . Figure 2a shows a spectrogram of an audio signal recorded over a telephone line and Figure 2b shows the long-term spectrum for the same audio signal. In both Figure 2a and 2b, one can see the tonal interferences, formant contribution, and noise affecting the long-term average. Thus, it is difficult to deduce which portions of the spectrum are due to channel effects, which portions are due to speech signal, and which portions are due to narrowband interferences or other noises.

Figure 2. Spectrogram of an audio signal and its long-term spectral average.

Signal Decomposition

Typically for audio signals, wideband or narrowband filters are applied to gain additional insight. However, if a narrowband filter is applied, the wideband information is still present and can cloud the picture. Likewise with

wideband filters, the narrowband information is still present and distorts the measurements. The desire is to approximate the spectral envelope of the long-term average before estimating h or x . Median averaging and smoothing could be employed to estimate the spectral envelope, however, the formants, narrowband interferences, and noise may still skew the estimate.

Due to the complexity of the audio signal, a signal decomposition technique was chosen to estimate the spectral envelope. The technique chosen for signal decomposition was the Adjustable Bandwidth Concept [1]. Instead of multi-resolution approaches, this technique first estimates the wideband portion of the signal and then removes the wideband portion from the original signal. For audio signals, the wideband information is mainly due to the nature of speech which typically falls in the frequency range of 60 to 12000 Hz. Next, the medium band portion is estimated. For audio signals, this tends to be the formant information. Finally, after the medium portion is removed, the narrowband portion is estimated. Narrowband information in audio signals tend to be from tonal interferences. Figure 3 shows the schematic for the ABC decomposition approach.

Figure 4a shows the resultant wideband portion after the ABC decomposition technique and Figure 4b shows the long-term spectrum for the wideband portion. Note that Figure 4b seems to be an excellent estimate of the spectral envelope. This estimate is then the starting point for trying to estimate either h or x . However, since one can not assume anything about h , the next step is to examine assumptions about speech production.

Figure 3. Signal Decomposition via the Adjustable Bandwidth Concept.

Figure 4. Wideband Response from the ABC technique and its long-term spectral average.

Speech Production

One model for speech production is the source-filter theory for vowel production. For this model, the glottal pulses, which are generated as the larynx opens and closes, are considered to be the source. The glottal pulses are then modified or filtered by the vocal tract.

The vocal tract is quite complex since it includes both oral and pharyngeal areas. Plus, in speech production, there is the additional coupling between the lips and the atmosphere. However, in the simplest case, the vocal tract can be assumed to be a quarter-wave resonator when the vocal folds are closed. For a quarter-wave resonator, the resonant frequencies are given by the equation:

$$F_n = \frac{c(2n-1)}{4L} \quad (2)$$

where n is the resonant number, c is the speed of sound which is approximately 340 m/s, and L is the length of the quarter-wave resonator. For the average male, the vocal tract length is about 17 cm. Thus, equation 2 can be rewritten as:

$$F_n = \frac{340(2n-1)}{4(0.17)} = 500(2n-1). \quad (3)$$

The first few resonances will be at 500 Hz, 1500 Hz, 2500 Hz, and 3500 Hz.

The goal of examining the source-filter theory is to derive an average estimate of x . As stated before, for a general solution, it is difficult to make any assumptions about h . Therefore, the approach is to use the spectral envelope of y that was previously derived along with an average estimate for x in order to glean information about the channel h .

In order to derive an average estimate of x , it is important to use data that was collected in a quiet environment with a high quality microphone. The TIMIT database was chosen for this experiment. It was collected for speech recognition development and contains 6300 phonetically transcribed sentences from 630 speakers of 8 dialect regions in the United States. For the average speech estimate, all the

males from dialect region 2 (Northern) and dialect region 3 (North Midland) were used. The three 'SI' sentences, which are unique for each speaker, were used. There were a total of 109 different speakers and, thus, 327 sentences. Figure 5 shows the 'average' male spectrum using the data set just described. Also note that the resonances appear at about 500, 1500, 2500, and 3500 Hz as predicted in Equation 3. Note that the ABC decomposition technique was first applied and only the wideband portion was used to estimate the average male spectrum.

In the frequency domain, Equation 3 is:

$$Y = HX. \quad (4)$$

Since both the estimate of y (see Figure 4b) and the estimate of x (see Figure 5) are in the log domain, Equation 4 can be used to solve for h by simply subtracting the average estimate of x from the estimate of y .

$$\log H = \log Y - \log X \quad (5)$$

Figure 5. Average Male Spectrum using ABC Decomposition.

3. LINEAR CHANNEL EXPERIMENTS

The preceding section presented an innovative approach for blindly estimating a channel given only the observed signal y . This section presents some experimental results using known linear channels. The first step is to select a wideband audio signal (from the dialect region 1 of TIMIT) and then convolve it with a known linear channel. This represents the channel corrupted data, y , of Equation 1. The ABC approach is then applied to y to get an estimate of the wideband portion (similar to Figure 4b). Finally, the average male spectrum is subtracted to give an estimate of h .

Figure 6 shows an example using this technique. The original wideband spectrum for the chosen audio (solid line) is seen in Figure 6a. Also, in Figure 6a is the average male estimate (dashed line). Obviously, the estimate will never be an exact match, however, it is clear that the estimate is reasonably close to the original speech spectrum. Figure 6b shows the original linear channel (solid line) and the

channel estimate (dashed line). Remarkably, the channel estimate is very close to the true channel.

While Figure 6 provides a good visual of how good this technique can be for linear channels, it does not provide a measure of performance to evaluate this technique. Thus, speaker identification experiments were chosen. The 24 males speakers from dialect region 1 of TIMIT were chosen for speaker identification experiments (note that the average male spectrum was computed from the 109 males speakers of dialect region 2 and dialect region 3).

In order to use this technique for speaker identification, the channel estimate needs to be used to compute an inverse filter and then the channel corrupted data needs to be filtered via the inverse filter coefficients. Thus, in these experiments, the goal is to restore the frequency information that was attenuated via the channel.

Figure 6. a) True input speech vs. average male spectrum. b) True channel vs. the estimated channel.

Table 1 gives the results for the 24 TIMIT speakers. Five sentences ('SA' and 'SI') were used to train a speaker model and the remaining five sentences ('SX') were individually scored against all the speaker models. Mel-features were used along with a vector quantizer (VQ) for the experiments. The first row gives the performance when TIMIT data is used for both the training and testing data. Thus, both training and testing consist of wideband audio and the performance is excellent as expected.

For the second and third row, either the training or testing data was corrupted by the carbon-button microphone response shown in Figure 1a. Once the data is corrupted, the channel estimation and inverse filter techniques are applied. Normally for mismatched conditions of this magnitude, the performance would be very low (about 10%). However, as seen in Table 1, the performance is above 80% for the wideband train/carbon-button test case and above 90% for the carbon-button train/wideband test. While the channel estimation and inverse filtering technique did not fully restore the speaker identification performance, the performance gains demonstrates that the channel estimation and inverse filtering must be performing well. Even if the exact inverse filter was used, not all the

frequency information would be restored due to strong attenuation in the stop band regions.

For the fourth and fifth row, either the training or testing data was corrupted by the electret microphone response shown in Figure 1b. Note that for this microphone, the roll-off at the higher frequencies is quite steep and severe. Thus, the inverse filtering is not able to restore all the frequency information and the speaker identification performance is lower than the carbon-button experiments.

Train	Test	Performance
Wideband	Wideband	97.5%
Wideband	Carbon	81.7%
Carbon	Wideband	92.5%
Wideband	Electret	70.0%
Electret	Wideband	84.2%

Table 1. Speaker Identification Performance.

4. NON-LINEAR CHANNEL EXPERIMENTS

Equation 1 was used to develop a technique to blindly estimate a channel. However, communication channels also contain additional noise and non-linear distortions. Thus, this section applies the same technique to telephone channel data where the channel conditions are no longer being simulated. NTIMIT data is used for these experiments. NTIMIT is TIMIT data that has been transmitted over a telephone. Along with the audio data, a 1 KHz tone and a sweeping tone from 10 Hz to 4000 Hz was also transmitted on the telephone line. The sweeping tone can be used to derive a channel estimate and thus provide some groundtruth information.

Figure 7 shows an example of NTIMIT audio. The solid line is the true channel as calculated from the sweeping tone. The dashed line is the blind estimate of the channel. While not perfect, the estimate still does a good job of capturing the shape and roll-offs. The key thing to note is that the low end and high end frequencies are noisy. Thus, even if the channel is estimated perfectly, one can not restore the frequency information since one would only be amplifying noise.

Figure 7. NTIMIT channel (solid) and the estimate (dashed).

Speaker identification experiments were conducted using the same set of speakers for NTIMIT. For telephone data, the mel-features were limited to the 350-3600 Hz range and cepstral normalization was applied. Unlike the TIMIT data, the performance for NTIMIT is significantly worse at 65%. By computing the inverse filter and bandlimiting the data to 350-3600 Hz, the performance for NTIMIT remained at 65%. While it is encouraging that the performance did not fall off anymore, this technique was not able to improve the speaker identification scores. For the TIMIT data, this technique was able to restore some of the frequency information at the low and high frequencies. However, for NTIMIT, there is only noise at the low and high frequencies. Thus, amplifying them by the inverse filter does not aid in speaker identification.

5. PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

Section 3 examined linear channel where a known linear channel was convolved with a wideband audio signal where the audio data was from the TIMIT database. For this section, the technique was fairly successful in restoring performance. However, using NTIMIT in Section 4, the technique was not able to restore performance. Thus, the question remains as to how to use and apply channel estimation in a realistic environment.

Speaker Database

For this section, an in-house telephone database was chosen which had poor speaker identification performance (about 58%). For this database, there are 46 speakers. Each speaker has one training file about 30 seconds in length and five test files, each about 30 seconds in length. For these 46 speakers, 17 speakers had all of their files scored correctly (an additional 5 speakers had 4/5 scored correctly) and 11 speakers had all of their files scored incorrectly (an additional 5 speakers had 4/5 scored incorrectly). Thus, out of the 46 speakers, only 8 speakers had a "mixed-bag" of correct/incorrect scores. The rest of the speakers were either at or near 100% or they were at or near 0%.

This database also contains multiple challenging conditions. It is telephone data which means it has a reduced bandwidth, some of the telephone calls are long distance which introduces additional noises and distortions, and a lot of the phone calls have additional hums and narrowband interferences. In addition to cross channel conditions, there are different speaking styles between the training and testing data. For the training data the speakers were asked to describe a photograph and thus the speech is more 'prescribed'. Perhaps, everybody used the same telephone while describing the photograph. For the testing data, the speech was more spontaneous and the speakers were allowed to talk about anything. The speakers seem to be calling from other locations such as their home. Thus, a different handset is being used, but it is assumed that the same recording equipment was used.

The goal is to examine the speakers and try to deduce why certain speakers scored very well and other speakers scored very poor. We know that speaker identification works very well in a clean, wideband environment. However, when mismatch conditions arise such as channel or SNR conditions, performance deteriorates.

Conditions and Features for Speaker Recognition

The following paragraphs lists the assumptions, techniques, and settings used for the speaker identification experiments.

Cepstral Features: A mel-feature from 500-3000 Hz is used as the feature. Since the data is telephone data, a restricted bandwidth is chosen. A few more speakers would be scored correctly if the bandwidth for the mel-feature had a wider bandwidth, however, more mismatch conditions would also be introduced at the band edges. This mel-feature has 14 coefficients for the bandwidth of 500-3000 Hz. It has an additional 14 coefficients of weighted mel-features. Thus, the total length of the feature is 28 (14 mel-features + 14 weighted mel-features). For this mel-feature and this database, 132 out of 230 speakers are scored correctly with the VQ and 131 out of 230 speakers are scored correctly with the GMM-UBM.

Classifiers: Both the VQ and GMM scores will be used to judge performance. For the VQ, 40 centroids are used and for the GMM, 16 mixtures are used. A UBM is also used with the GMM. The UBM is developed from another telephone database. Unlike other UBMS, fewer mel-features are used here and, thus, it was not necessary to have large mixture models of 1024 to achieve good performance. For this data set and these features, GMM scores (higher is better) less than 1 are weak, scores between 1 and 2 are okay, and scores greater than 2 are strong.

Channel Estimations: For each test file, the test file channel is compared to the training file channel and a difference is computed. Since the magnitude of the channel does not impact the speaker id performance, a threshold of 3 dB is used for computing the difference between the two estimates. For the FFT bins between 500 and 3000 Hz, the channel difference at each bin is compared to the threshold of 3 dB. If the difference between a training bin and a

testing bin is greater than the 3 dB threshold, it is added to the cumulative sum. Otherwise, it is not counted in the cumulative sum.

Test Results

In this section, multiple features will be used to weed out the weaker results. The goal is to be able to label the speaker recognition as being low, medium, or high confidence. This section examines the data for speaker identification. For speaker identification, the goal is to find the training model that has the closest match with the test file. For the confidence rating, the winning speaker (whether it's the correct speaker or not) will then be labeled as high, medium, or low confidence.

The 230 files are all assumed to have an initial rating of medium confidence. The GMM scores 131/230 (57.0%) correctly and the VQ scores 132/230 (57.4%) correctly. Both classifiers used the same mel-feature with cepstral-mean-subtraction. Thus, the only difference is the classifier type. A multi-step approach is used to find the weak matches and/or the strong matches.

Step 1, Classifier Output: The first step is to compare the top choice of the VQ and GMM classifier. If both classifiers choose the same speaker as top choice (albeit it may not be the correct speaker), the test files retain a medium confidence rating. If the two classifiers have a different speaker as a top choice, the test file is bumped to a low confidence rating and discarded. Of the 230 files, 156 files retain their medium confidence rating. Thus, 74 are discarded. Of the 156 files, 115/156 (73.7%) files are scored correctly.

Step 2, Channel Match: As explained before, this feature looks at the channel difference between the test file and the winning training model. For this step (and subsequent steps), the test file is compared against the winning speaker (even if the winning speaker is the incorrect speaker). If the difference for each bin is > 3 dB, the difference is counted in the cumulative sum. Otherwise, it is not. For this feature, the threshold for the cumulative sum was set at 100. If the channel difference is below 100, then, the confidence rating remains at medium confidence. If the channel difference is greater than or equal to 100, the file is bumped to low confidence and discarded. 40 files are discarded and 116 remain. 97/116 (83.6%) are scored correct.

Step 3, GMM Score: The UBM helps to build in some robustness and also provides some normalization. Thus, the GMM-UBM score is a reliable measure of how close two files match. If the GMM score is < 1.0 , the match is considered to be a poor match. Thus, the file is considered to have low confidence and is discarded. Using this approach, 14 additional files are discarded and 102 remain. 90/102 (88.2%) files are scored correct.

Step 4, SNR: If the training file has too low of an SNR, the training model is in suspect and may be easily confused with other speakers. If the training SNR is < 15 dB and the model is chosen as the top choice for a test file, the test file

is labeled as having low confidence. Using this approach, 15 more files are discarded and 87 remain. 80/87 (92.0%) are scored correct.

Step 5, GMM Score: The first 4 steps were looking for files to discard (bump to low confidence). 143 files were discarded and 87 files remain. Of these 87 files, 80 are scored correct by the two classifiers (92.0%). This step is looking for files to move to high confidence. If the GMM score is > 2.0 , the file is moved to high confidence. 26 files are rated as high confidence and 25/26 (96.2%) are scored correct. The one file that was scored incorrectly had a serious of tones throughout the frequency band and thus should also be discarded. Therefore, 25/25 (100%) are labeled as high confidence.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a new technique for blindly estimating channels for audio signals. The first step of the technique was to estimate the spectral envelope via the ABC decomposition technique. The second step was to subtract off, in the log domain, an average male spectrum which is an estimate of the input. The resulting signal represents the channel estimate. If the attenuation is not too severe, the information can be restored along with speaker identification performance. However, in the NTIMIT case, the performance was not improved. Visual graphs were also provided along with the speaker identification experiments to demonstrate that this technique is able to reliably estimate the channel in a blind fashion.

By applying the channel estimation techniques to both the training and testing file, channel mismatch conditions were identified. A telephone database was used to demonstrate that by using multiple techniques, the good matches could be identified and the suspect matches could be discarded. Of the 230 files, 87 files were retained after passing the first four steps. Of these 87 files, 80/87 (92.0%) were scored correct. In addition, a subset of 25 speakers was also identified as having high confidence. All 25 files were scored correct by both classifiers. Thus, for this database, channel estimation and channel mismatch identification were an important contributor to the success of accurately identifying those files of high confidence. This is no small feat being that the original success rate for the 230 test files was only about 58%.

REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHY

Stanley Wenzel received his B.S. degree in Electrical Engineering from Iowa State University in 1987. He

received his M.S. and Ph.D. in *Electrical Engineering* from Colorado State University in 1991 and 1997 respectively. Since 1994, he has been employed by the Air Force Research Laboratory in Rome, New York where his research interests are in channel estimation, speaker model mitigation, confidence scores, open-set modeling, dialect identification, and noise removal.

Andrew Noga received the B.S. degree in Electrical Engineering from Clarkson College of Technology, Potsdam NY, in 1983, and the M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in Electrical Engineering from Syracuse University, Syracuse NY, in 1988 and 1995, respectively. He has been an engineer with the Rome Research Site of AFRL, Rome, NY since 1983 where his work has focused on discrete-time communications signal processing, including detection and parameter estimation, multivariate statistical analyses, spectral characterization, demodulation, and cochannel interference mitigation.